

Gut Microbiota: A Critical Regulator of Health and Disease. A narrative review

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The gut microbiota, composed of trillions of microorganisms residing in the human gastrointestinal tract, plays a fundamental role in maintaining host health and influencing disease pathogenesis. The composition of this microbial community is host specific, evolving throughout an individual's lifetime and susceptible to both exogenous and endogenous modifications. Beyond aiding digestion, the gut microbiota regulates immune function, metabolism, neurological signaling, and protection against pathogens. Dysbiosis, or disruption in the microbial balance, has been linked to a wide range of diseases including obesity, diabetes, inflammatory bowel disease, cancer, and neuropsychiatric conditions. This review explores the composition and functions of the gut microbiota, its interactions with the host, the consequences of microbial imbalance, and emerging therapeutic strategies aimed at modulating the microbiota for improved health outcomes.

Keywords: Microbiome, Dysbiosis, microorganisms, Proteobacteria.

INTRODUCTION

The human microbiota comprises a vast community of microorganisms, including bacteria, yeasts, and viruses that inhabit various body sites, such as the gut, skin, lungs, and oral cavity (Ursell et al., 2014, Hou et al., 2022). This microbial community was first identified in the early 1900s and its composition is influenced by diet (David et al., 2014), environment (Ursell et al., 2013), host genetics (Benson et al., 2010) contact with other humans and animals, and temporal variations (Caporaso et al., 2011). Although the terms "microbiota" and "microbiome" are often used interchangeably, they have distinct meanings. *Microbiota* refers to the community of living microorganisms present in a specific environment, such as the gut or oral cavity. In contrast, the *microbiome* encompasses the complete genetic material of these

microorganisms, along with their structural components, metabolic products, and the surrounding environmental factors (Berg et al., 2020). The human gut is home to a complex and dynamic community of microorganisms, collectively known as the gut microbiota, that includes bacteria, archaea, viruses, and fungi³. These microbial populations form a symbiotic relationship with their host, contributing significantly to physiological homeostasis. They are the primary mediators of body homeostasis, impacting various physiological activities, such as metabolism, barrier homeostasis, inflammation, and hematopoiesis through both intestinal and extra-intestinal actions (Afzaal et al., 2022). The gut microbiota has recently been classified as a "vital organ" because of its multidirectional and communicational connection or axis with other organs through neural, endocrine, humoral, immunological, and metabolic pathways (Wu et al., 2025). Advances in next-generation sequencing technologies have revealed that alterations in the gut

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Table 1: Variation in microbial numbers and composition across the gastrointestinal tract

GI Tract	Density (cells/gram)	Microbiota Composition
Stomach	10^1	<i>Lactobacillus</i> , <i>VelliOnella</i> , <i>Hellicobacter</i>
Duodenum	10^3	<i>Bacilli</i> , <i>Streptococaceae</i> ,
Jejunum	10^4	<i>Actinomycinaeae</i> ,
Ileum	10^7	<i>Corynebacteriaceae</i>
Colon	10^{12}	<i>Lachnospiraceae</i> , <i>Bacteroidetes</i>

microbiota can profoundly affect health, triggering or exacerbating various diseases (Yang et al., 2025). Understanding the critical roles of gut microbiota is essential in unraveling new preventative and therapeutic approaches for modern diseases.

Composition and Development of the Gut Microbiota

Within the gut, microbial composition varies across different regions (shown in table 1), including the duodenum, ileum, and colon (Sartor, 2008), reflecting the complexity and specialization of these niches. Although the gut microbiota resides primarily in the digestive tract, its influence extends far beyond local functions. The gut microbiota begins to establish itself at birth, influenced by factors such as mode of delivery (vaginal vs. cesarean), breastfeeding, environment, antibiotic use, and diet. In adults, the dominant bacterial phyla include Firmicutes, Bacteroidetes, Actinobacteria, and Proteobacteria (Laterza et al., 2016). The most extensively researched fungi in the gut mycobiota include *Candida*, *Saccharomyces*, *Malassezia*, and *Cladosporium* (Auchtung et al., 2018). Besides bacteria and fungi, the human gut microbiota also consists of viruses, bacteriophages, and archaea—primarily *Methanobrevibacter smithii* (Lozupone et al., 2012). The composition is relatively stable but can be modulated by diet, lifestyle, stress, and medications (Fassarella et al., 2021).

Gut bacteria perform several essential roles, including food fermentation, defense against harmful microbes, stimulation of the immune system, and synthesis of vitamins (Hossain et al., 2022). In recent years, extensive research has emphasized the link between microbiota and various diseases, including cancer, diabetes, and neurological conditions (Rumyantsev et al., 2024) (as shown in Table 2). Additionally, altering the composition of the human microbiota holds significant potential for therapeutic interventions

FUNCTIONAL ROLES OF GUT MICROBIOTA IN HEALTH

Metabolic Functions

The gut microbiota plays a vital role in human metabolism by providing enzymes that the human genome does not

encode. These enzymes aid in processes such as breaking down polysaccharides and dietary fibers with production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) like butyrate, acetate, and propionate, as well as synthesis of vitamins (Steinert et al., 2025). When carbohydrates are available, saccharolytic fermentation by these bacteria typically generates beneficial metabolites. However, in the absence of sufficient carbohydrates, the bacteria shift to other energy sources, leading to the production of metabolites that may have harmful effects on human health (Boyd et al., 2013). The three predominant short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs) found in feces are acetate, propionate, and butyrate, typically occurring in molar ratios between 3:1:1 and 10:2:1 (Mukhopadhy and Louis, 2025). These proportions are similar to those observed in the intestines of individuals who died suddenly at an early age (Mukhopadhy and Louis, 2025). The three primary SCFAs each play distinct yet vital roles in the human body. Among them, butyrate is often considered the most crucial for health. It serves as the main energy source for colonocytes and may possess anti-cancer properties by promoting apoptosis in colon cancer cells and regulating gene expression through the inhibition of histone deacetylases (Wang et al., 2019; Steliou et al., 2012).

Immune Regulation

Immune system development begins at birth, triggered by initial exposure to microbiota. Full maturation depends on continuous interaction with commensal microbes, which help prevent chronic inflammation and dysregulated immune responses (Tibbs et al., 2019). Experimental models, such as germ-free (GF) animals, have illustrated the essential role of gut flora in shaping immune function (Uzbay, 2019). Germ-free animals exhibit underdeveloped immune structures, including poorly formed spleens, lymph nodes, and hypo plastic Peyer's patches. They also show reduced numbers of IgA-producing plasma cells and lower levels of secretory antibodies such as IgA and IgG (Macpherson and Harris, 2004). The gut microbiota plays a central role in training and regulating the host immune system. Commensal bacteria promote immune tolerance, while a diverse microbiota enhances resistance to infections and reduces the risk of autoimmune disorders. The gut microbiota plays a pivotal role in human health, particularly in

supporting and regulating the immune system (Afzaal et al., 2022). Its influence on mucosal immunity is especially notable, given that the intestinal mucosa represents the body's largest interface with external antigens (Afzaal et al., 2022). This mucosal surface is densely lined with microbes, making the gut microbiota a major source of antigenic stimuli that interact with the host's immune system. These microbial antigens activate pattern recognition receptors such as Toll-like receptors (TLRs) and NOD-like receptors (NLRs) located on intestinal epithelial cells (Stephen-Victor et al., 2025). To maintain immune balance, the gut tolerates commensal microbes while restricting microbial overgrowth and preventing translocation beyond the intestine (Sekirov et al., 2010).

Gut Microbiota and Malnutrition

Malnutrition, particularly undernutrition, can modulate gut microbiota composition (Flint et al., 2015). Due to ethical limitations, studies on the effects of nutrient deficiency on the microbiota are typically performed in animal models. In one such study, prolonged nutrient deprivation led to increased microbial diversity in mice, fish, and toads; however, geckos exhibited decreased diversity, while no significant changes were observed in quails (Kohl et al., 2014). These findings highlight the complexity and species-specific responses of microbiota to nutritional deficits. In Bangladeshi children with marasmus, characterized by severe energy deficiency, microbial diversity was significantly reduced. The gut microbiota in these children was dominated by Proteobacteria (46%). It had diminished levels of Bacteroidetes (18%), compared to healthy counterparts in whom Proteobacteria and Bacteroidetes accounted for 5% and 44%, respectively (Monira et al., 2011). A study involving 317 pairs of Malawian twins found that in 43% of the pairs, only one twin developed kwashiorkor. Serial analysis of their gut microbiota showed that microbial maturity improved temporarily with high-protein dietary supplements but reverted after supplementation ceased. Remarkably, transplanting gut microbiota from kwashiorkor-affected children into gnotobiotic mice, along with a Malawian diet, led to significant weight loss and disturbances in amino acid and carbohydrate metabolism in the recipient mice (Smith et al., 2025). These findings strongly suggest that the gut microbiome plays a significant role in the pathogenesis of malnutrition.

Gut Dysbiosis and Disease:

Metabolic Disorders

Dietary patterns and environmental factors strongly shape the composition and functionality of the gut microbiota. Diets high in fat, particularly Western-style diets, disrupt microbial communities and contribute to metabolic disorders such as obesity, type 2 diabetes, and

metabolic syndrome. Similarly, disruptions in the circadian rhythm, caused by irregular sleep, shift work, or erratic feeding, can disturb microbial balance and increase susceptibility to inflammatory diseases, including inflammatory bowel disease and certain types of cancer (Reynolds et al., 2017).

Evidence linking the gut microbiota to obesity initially came from germ-free mouse models. Colonization of these mice with microbiota from conventionally raised counterparts resulted in increased fat accumulation and insulin resistance despite reduced food intake, indicating that microbiota enhance dietary energy harvest (Bäckhed et al., 2004). Obesity is consistently associated with a microbial profile characterized by elevated Firmicutes and reduced Bacteroidetes, correlating with increased expression of carbohydrate-metabolizing genes and the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), which enhances the extraction of energy from otherwise indigestible polysaccharides (Ley et al., 2005; Turnbaugh et al., 2006). Germ-free mice inoculated with microbiota from obese donors gained more fat than those colonized with microbiota from lean donors, despite identical caloric intake (Turnbaugh et al., 2006; B.-N. Liu et al., 2021). Similar trends were observed in genetic models of obesity, such as *ob/ob* and *fa/fa* mice, which show elevated serum triglycerides, reduced Bifidobacteria, and increased genera including *Halomonas* and *Sphingomonas* (Waldram et al., 2009). Human studies mirror these findings. Using 16S rRNA sequencing, Duan et al. (2021) reported a reduction in microbial diversity among obese individuals. Alterations in the Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratio are frequently observed, with increased *Prevotella*, *Megamonas*, *Fusobacterium*, and *Blautia*, alongside reductions in beneficial genera such as *Faecalibacterium* and *Clostridium* cluster XIVa.

A central mechanism linking the gut microbiota and obesity is microbial fermentation of dietary fibers and resistant starches into SCFAs, including acetate, propionate, and butyrate. These SCFAs act as energy substrates and signaling molecules that activate transcription factors such as carbohydrate-responsive element-binding protein (ChREBP) and sterol regulatory element-binding protein 1 (SREBP1), while suppressing fasting-induced adipocyte factor (FIAF). FIAF suppression enhances lipoprotein lipase (LPL) activity, promoting triglyceride uptake and fat storage (Festi et al., 2014; Khan et al., 2016). The gut microbiota also influences appetite and energy balance through the gut-brain axis, regulating secretion of gut hormones such as peptide YY (PYY), glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1), and pancreatic polypeptide (Shajib & Khan, 2015; Y. Wu et al., 2019; Salehi & Purnell, 2019). Dysregulation of these pathways contributes to overeating and weight gain.

Circadian regulation is another pathway linking microbiota and obesity. Microbial signals activate histone deacetylase 3 (HDAC3) in intestinal epithelial cells, driving rhythmic expression of nutrient transporters such

Table 2: Gut Microbial Diversity of Different Diseases

Animal Specie	Diseases	Sub Group	Modification in Gut Microbial Diversity Attributed to Disease	References
Human	Obesity		<i>Erectale</i> ↑, <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i> ↑, <i>Oscillibacter valericigenes</i> ↑, <i>Bacteroides =Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i> = <i>Collinsella aerofaciens</i> ↓, <i>Roseburia/Eubacterium</i> ↑, <i>Bifidobacterium</i> ↑, <i>Prevotella</i> ↑, <i>Xylanibacter</i> ↑, <i>B. vulgatus</i> ↓, <i>Eubacterium</i> ↑, <i>Oscillibacter</i> ↑, <i>Butyricoccus</i> ↑, <i>Sporobacter</i> ↑, <i>Blautia</i> ↓, <i>Dorea</i> ↓, <i>Lachnospiraceae</i> ↓, <i>Roseburia</i> ↓, <i>Faecalibacterium</i> ↓, <i>Ruminococcus</i> ↓, <i>Erysipelotrichaceae</i> ↓, <i>Succinivibrio</i> ↑, <i>Treponema</i> ↑, <i>Bacteroides</i> ↑, <i>Alistipes</i> ↑, <i>Barnesiella</i> ↑, <i>Roseburia</i> ↓, <i>Eubacterium rectale</i> ↓, <i>Ruminococcus bromii</i> ↓, <i>Bilophila</i> ↑,	(136) (137) (138) (139) (140) (141)
Sprague-Dawley rats	Obesity		<i>Bacteroidales</i> ↑, <i>Clostridiales</i> ↑,	(142)
Mice	Obesity		<i>Eubacterium dolichum</i> ↑,	(143)
RELMβ KO and wild-type mice	Obesity		<i>Desulfovibrionaceae</i> ↑, <i>Bacteroidaceae</i> ↓, <i>Prevotella</i> ↓, <i>Rickenellaceae</i> ↓,	(144)
ob/ob mice			<i>Bifidobacteria</i> ↑, <i>Actinobacteria</i> ↑, <i>Proteobacteria</i> ↓,	(145)
Humans	Diabetes (Type 2)		Family: <i>Lachnospiraceae</i> ↑, <i>Erysipelotrichaceae</i> ↓ Genus: <i>Alistipes</i> ↑, <i>Clostridium</i> ↑, <i>Eubacterium</i> ↓, <i>Faecalibacterium</i> ↓, <i>Subdoligranulum</i> ↑, <i>Parabacteroides</i> ↑ Species: <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i> ↑, <i>Bacteroides intestinalis</i> ↑, <i>Clostridium bolteae</i> ↑, <i>Clostridium hatheway</i> ↑, <i>Clostridium ramosum</i> ↑, <i>Clostridium symbiosum</i> ↑, <i>Eggerthella lenta</i> ↑, <i>Escherichia coli</i> ↑, <i>Eubacterium rectale</i> ↓, <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i> ↓, <i>Haemophilus parainfluenzae</i> ↓, <i>Roseburia intestinalis</i> ↓, <i>Roseburia inulinivorans</i> ↓ Genus: <i>Akkermansia</i> ↑, <i>Alistipes</i> ↑, <i>Bacteroides</i> ↓, <i>Bilophila</i> ↑, <i>Catenibacterium</i> ↓, <i>Dialister</i> ↑, <i>Dorea</i> ↑, <i>Erysipelotrichaceae</i> IS ↑, <i>Lachnospiraceae</i> IS ↓, <i>Lactobacillus</i> ↑, <i>Parabacteroides</i> ↑, <i>Prevotella</i> ↑, <i>Roseburia</i> ↓, <i>Ruminococcus</i> ↓, <i>Sporobacter</i> ↑, <i>Subdoligranulum</i> ↓, <i>Succinivibrio</i> ↑, <i>Sutterella</i> ↑ Species: <i>Dorea longicatena</i> ↓ Genus: <i>Abiotrophia</i> ↑, <i>Collinsella</i> ↑, <i>Dorea</i> ↑, <i>Eubacterium</i> ↑, <i>Haemophilus</i> ↓, <i>Megamonas</i> ↓, <i>Peptostreptococcus</i> ↑, <i>Prevotella</i> ↑, <i>Roseburia</i> ↓, <i>Sporobacter</i> ↑, <i>Subdoligranulum</i> ↑ Genus: <i>Allisonella</i> ↑, <i>Bacillus</i> ↓, <i>Christensenellaceae_R_7</i> ↑, <i>Dialister</i> ↑, <i>Escherichia Shigella</i> ↓, <i>Eubacterium coprostanoligenes</i> groups ↑, <i>Lactobacillus</i> ↑, <i>Prevotella_9</i> ↓, <i>Ruminococcus_2</i> ↓, <i>Subdoligranulum</i> ↑	(146) (147) (148) (149)
Human	Autoimmune Diseases	Inflammatory Bowel Disease	<i>E. coli</i> ↑ <i>H.pylori</i> ↑ <i>Clostridium leptum</i> ↓ <i>Faecalibacterium prausnitzii</i> , ↓ <i>C. coccoides</i> and <i>C. leptum</i> ↓ <i>F. prausnitzii</i> ↓	(2) (150) (151)

Table 2. Contd.

		Ulcerative Colitis	<i>Lactobacillus plantarum</i> sc-5↓ <i>Bifidobacterium longum</i> ↓ <i>Limosilactobacillus mucosae</i> ↓ <i>Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus</i> ↓	(152) (153) (154) (155)
Human	Cancer	Colorectal cancer	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i> ↑ <i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> ↑, <i>Porphyromonas asaccharolytica</i> ↑, <i>Parvimonas micra</i> ↑, <i>Prevotella intermedia</i> ↓, <i>Alistipes finegoldii</i> ↑ and <i>Thermanaerovibrio acidaminovorans</i> ↑ <i>Peptostreptococcus anaerobius</i>	(156) (157) (158) (159)
Human		gastric cancer	<i>Fusobacterium nucleatum</i> ↑	(160)
Human		Hepatocellular cancer	<i>Dietziaceae</i> ↑, <i>Pseudomonadaceae</i> ↑, <i>Oxalobacteraceae</i> ↑	(161) (162)
APPS1 mice	Neurodegeneration	Alzheimer's Disease	<i>Allobaculum</i> ↓ <i>Akkermansia</i> ↓ <i>Rikenellaceae</i> ↑	(163)
Human			<i>Ruminococcus</i> ↓ <i>Faecalibacterium</i> , <i>Lachnospira</i> ↓ <i>Dialister</i> ↓ <i>Lachnoclostridium</i> ↓ <i>Roseburia</i> abundance ↓ <i>Phascolarctobacterium</i> ↑ <i>Lactobacillus</i> ↑ <i>Akkermansia muciniphila</i> ↑	(164)
Human		Parkinson's Disease	<i>Lactobacillus gasseri</i> ↑ <i>Bacteroides fragilis</i> ↓ <i>Clostridium coccoides</i> ↓ <i>Prevotellaceae</i> ↓, <i>Verrucomicrobiaceae</i> ↑	(165) (105) (166)
		Multiple Sclerosis	<i>Streptococcus sp.</i> ↑ <i>Eggerthella sp.</i> ↑ <i>Bifidobacterium</i> ↑, <i>Acinetobacter</i> ↑, <i>Corynebacterium</i> ↑, <i>Megamonas</i> ↑, <i>Actinomyces</i> ↑, <i>Mogibacterium</i> ↑, <i>Bulleidia</i> ↑ <i>Parabacteroides</i> ↓, <i>Prevotella</i> ↓, <i>Serratia</i> ↓, <i>Clostridium</i> ↓, <i>Aquamonas</i> ↓, <i>Bacillus</i> ↓, <i>Acidaminococcus</i> ↓, <i>Faecalibacterium</i> ↓, <i>Prevotella</i> ↓, <i>Anaerostipes</i> ↓, <i>Clostridia cluster IV and XIVa spp.</i> ↓	(116) (121)

as Cd36, which enhances fat absorption (Rácz et al., 2018; Kuang et al., 2019) Microbiota also modulate nuclear factor IL-3 regulator (NFIL3), further linking microbial composition with host circadian metabolism. Population-based studies highlight bacterial taxa associated with lean or obese phenotypes. Christensenellaceae, Methanobacteriales, *Lactobacillus*, *Bifidobacterium*, and *Akkermansia muciniphila* are enriched in lean individuals and considered anti-obesogenic (Waters & Ley, 2019; Depommier et al., 2019). In contrast, obese Indian adults have higher levels of *Bacteroides* and Archaea, alongside elevated fecal SCFAs (47). Obese Swedish children exhibited increased Enterobacteriaceae and decreased *Desulfovibrio* and Akkermansiaceae (Karlsson et al., 2012).

Gut Microbiota and Diabetes

Numerous studies have linked alterations in gut microbiota composition to the development of diabetes. Epidemiological evidence indicates that reduced microbial diversity is a common feature in diabetic patients (Gowd et al., 2019). The intake of dietary fiber is inversely associated with the incidence of type 2 diabetes (T2D), with higher fiber consumption linked to increased

microbial diversity and altered Firmicutes/Bacteroidetes ratios (Martínez-Carrillo et al., 2024). Fiber also enhances microbial fermentation, increasing the production of short-chain fatty acids (SCFAs), which act as ligands for the free fatty acid receptor 2 (FFAR2) and free fatty acid receptor 3 (FFAR3), thereby regulating glucose homeostasis (Gholizadeh et al., 2019). Soluble fiber further lowers blood glucose by increasing gastric viscosity, delaying gastric emptying, prolonging intestinal transit, and reducing the rate of glucose absorption, which modifies postprandial glucose and cholesterol concentrations (Fuller et al., 2016).

Several microbial taxa exert protective roles against diabetes. *Lactobacillus fermentum*, *Lactobacillus plantarum*, *Lactobacillus casei*, *Roseburia intestinalis*, *Akkermansia muciniphila*, and *Bacteroides fragilis* have improved glucose metabolism and insulin sensitivity while suppressing proinflammatory cytokines (Iatcu et al., 202). Conversely, reductions in butyrate-producing species, such as *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Roseburia intestinalis*, are strongly associated with the onset of type 2 diabetes (T2D) (Karlsson et al., 2013). The inhibition of butyrate producers with vancomycin induces insulin resistance (Vrieze et al., 2014). In contrast, propionate also impairs insulin signaling by promoting the expression

of glucagon and fatty acid-binding protein 4 (FABP4) in mice, as well as elevating norepinephrine, glucagon, and FABP4 in humans (Tirosh et al., 2019)..

Inflammatory Bowel Diseases (IBD)

Patients with Crohn's disease (CD) and ulcerative colitis exhibit reduced microbial diversity and increased abundance of pathogenic bacteria. Dysbiosis contributes to mucosal inflammation and epithelial barrier disruption (Caparrós et al., 2021). In Crohn's disease patients, host-microbe interactions become harmful, characterized by significant alterations at the strain level, a reduction in microbial diversity, and changes in several specific microbial metabolites. Clinical studies report reduced *Faecalibacterium prausnitzii* and *Roseburia* in CD, correlating with impaired SCFA synthesis (Liu et al., 2021). In murine models, *Bifidobacterium longum* Bar 33 and *Lactobacillus acidophilus* Bar 13 promoted the differentiation of Treg cells and reduced inflammation (Roselli et al., 2009) protecting against CD. *Lactobacillus casei* DN-114 001 enhanced CD4⁺ FoxP3⁺ Treg activity, alleviating colitis (Hacini-Rachinel et al., 2009) while microbial metabolites such as polysaccharide A from *Bacteroides fragilis* and products from *Enterobacter ludwigii* further promote Treg differentiation and suppress disease severity (Carasso et al., 2024, Li et al., 2022). While many studies focus on stool samples, recent findings reveal that the mucosal and mucus-associated microbiota contains communities distinct from fecal microbiota in their abundance, metabolism, activity, and replication patterns. This highlights the mucus layer as an area of special interest in Crohn's disease, which remains insufficiently explored.

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a subtype of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD), presents with recurrent intestinal inflammation. Studies showed reduced diversity and increased proinflammatory taxa, including *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella*, *Proteus*, and *Fusobacteria* (Mukhopadhyaya et al., 2012, Lupp et al., 2007). Protective commensals and SCFAs further decreases, weakening mucosal tolerance (Yang et al., 2020). Reduced levels of fecal acetate and butyrate have been reported in patients with UC (Marchesi et al., 2007). Personalized interventions such as dietary fiber enrichment or targeted probiotics are potential management strategies (Zeevi et al., 2019).

Cancer

The human gut microbiota plays a crucial role in maintaining health and preventing disease, including the development of cancer. Microbial dysbiosis contributes to carcinogenesis by inducing chronic inflammation, altering host immune responses, and producing carcinogenic metabolites (Meng et al., 2018, Zitvogel et al., 2017). Approximately 20% of global cancer cases are associated with pathogens such as *Helicobacter pylori*,

Fusobacterium nucleatum, human papillomavirus (HPV), and Epstein-Barr virus (Zitvogel et al., 2017; Cheng et al., 2020). Both clinical and experimental evidence demonstrate that disturbances in microbial balance not only drive tumor initiation and progression but also affect the efficacy of anticancer therapies (Cheng et al., 2020).

Gastric cancer (GC) which is strongly associated with *H. pylori* infection, induces chronic inflammation and immune activation that disrupts epithelial homeostasis (Doorakkers et al., 2016.. This bacterium upregulates cytokine production and oncogenic signaling, driving DNA damage and tumor growth (Lupp et al., 2007, Yang et al., 2020) Dysbiosis of the gastric microbiota, characterized by a shift from Gram-positive Firmicutes to Gram-negative anaerobes, further exacerbates the pathology and progression. Both human and animal studies confirm that persistent *H. pylori* infection promotes tumorigenesis, while eradication reduces risk (Doorakkers et al., 2016). Enrichment of lactic acid-producing bacteria such as *Lactococcus* and *Lactobacillus*, together with short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) production pathways, has been reported in GC biopsies (Castaño-Rodríguez et al., 2017). Nevertheless, *H. pylori* remains the central driver. Classified as a class I carcinogen, it reduces microbial diversity in the gastric niche (Kumar et al., 2020) and relies on virulence factors such as cytotoxin-associated gene A (CagA) and vacuolating cytotoxin A (VacA) to promote carcinogenesis (Hayashi et al., 2013, Sun et al., 2013).

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC), often arising in cirrhosis or fatty liver disease, is shaped by gut-liver microbial interactions (Tilg et al., 2016). Secondary bile acids (BA), generated by *Clostridium spp.*, induce oxidative stress and DNA damage (Ridlon et al., 2006), while LPS from Gram-negative bacteria activate Toll-like receptor 4, enhancing hepatic inflammation (Ajouz et al., 2014). Cirrhosis and HCC are associated with increased levels of *Bacteroides*, *Ruminococcaceae*, and *E. coli*, alongside depletion of SCFA-producing bacteria (Ren et al., 2019).

Colorectal cancer (CRC), the third most common cancer worldwide, is strongly influenced by gut microbiota composition. Dysbiosis promotes tumorigenesis through the action of carcinogens, inflammatory mediators, and DNA-damaging metabolites. Germ-free or probiotic-supplemented mice resist colitis-associated cancer, while dysbiotic microbiota enhances tumor formation. Key pathogens include enterotoxigenic *Bacteroides fragilis* (ETBF), which initiates carcinogenesis via chronic inflammation, epithelial barrier disruption, and immune modulation. It enables opportunistic "passenger" bacteria such as *F. nucleatum* to accelerate progression..

Neuropsychiatric Conditions

Research has found distinct changes in the microbiome

of people with conditions such as depression, Alzheimer's disease, and autism. In parallel, metabolites produced by these microbes can influence the creation of neurotransmitters and drive neuro-inflammatory processes in the brain (Radjabzadeh et al., 2022, Gao et al., 2023). Multiple animal studies have demonstrated that transferring gut microbiota from individuals with depressive disorder into healthy animals can trigger behaviors resembling depression. In contrast, introducing microbiota from healthy donors has been shown to alleviate depressive-like symptoms in these animal models. Disruption of the gut microbiome, marked by changes in microbial composition, decreased diversity, and functional imbalance, can influence neural pathways linked to cognitive deterioration and neurodegeneration, positioning it as an important contributor to Alzheimer's disease development and progression. Certain gut microbial strains have been linked to cognitive performance and neuropsychiatric manifestations in individuals with Alzheimer's disease. Additionally, evidence suggests that probiotic supplementation could serve as a beneficial dietary strategy for managing Alzheimer's disease as well as other conditions, including polycystic ovarian syndrome and major depressive disorder; Kang et al., 2025). A growing body of research highlights the contribution of gut microbial imbalances to the development of autism spectrum disorder, suggesting that restoring healthy gut microbial communities may help alleviate both gastrointestinal disturbances and neurobehavioral symptoms associated with autism spectrum disorder. Notably, a Phase I clinical trial of fecal microbiota transplantation demonstrated sustained improvements in autism spectrum disorder-related behaviors and digestive symptoms over a two-year follow-up period.

Neurobehavioral Impact

The gut–brain axis is a bidirectional communication system that links the gastrointestinal tract, the central nervous system (CNS), and the gut microbiota through neural, endocrine, and immune pathways. This network regulates digestion, immunity, mood, cognition, and behavior. Disruption of microbial balance, known as dysbiosis, contributes to gastrointestinal disorders and triggers systemic inflammation through the release of lipopolysaccharides (LPS), proinflammatory cytokines, and the activation of monocytes. These responses impair intestinal and blood–brain barrier integrity, facilitating the progression of neurodegenerative diseases such as amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), Alzheimer's disease (AD), Parkinson's disease (PD), and multiple sclerosis (MS). External factors, including diet, circadian rhythm disturbances, sedentary lifestyle, and stress, further influence microbiota composition, thereby affecting brain function and disease susceptibility (Sonnenburg and Sonnenburg ED. 2019, Irwin and Opp MR. 2017)).

Parkinson's disease (PD) arises from progressive degeneration of dopaminergic neurons in the substantia nigra, leading to dopamine deficiency and motor symptoms such as tremor, rigidity, and bradykinesia, alongside non-motor features including cognitive decline. Dysbiosis significantly contributes to PD pathogenesis, with case–control studies reporting reduced Prevotellaceae and *Clostridium coccoides*, and increased Enterococcaceae and Lactobacillaceae in patients. Altered gut permeability, bacterial overgrowth, and loss of SCFA–producing bacteria such as Roseburia and Faecalibacterium have also been reported in PD cases (Nuzum et al., 2020 and Tan et al., 2014)

Alzheimer's disease (AD), the leading cause of dementia, is characterized by extracellular amyloid- β plaques, tau tangles, and progressive memory and cognitive decline. Microbial imbalance in AD shows a reduction in Firmicutes and Actinobacteria, accompanied by an increase in Bacteroidetes and Ruminococcus, which correlates with neuroinflammation and cognitive deficits (Zhang, 2017, Ling, 2021). In mouse models, gut dysbiosis accelerates amyloid deposition and glial activation, whereas fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) from healthy donors reduces plaques and improves cognition (Minter et al., 2016, Kim et al., 2020).

Multiple sclerosis (MS) is a chronic inflammatory demyelinating disorder of the CNS, manifesting primarily as relapsing–remitting MS (RRMS) or primary progressive MS (PPMS) (Vidal-Jordana and Montalban, 2017, Goldenberg, 2012). Although the precise etiology remains unclear, immune dysregulation is a central component. Alterations in gut microbiota include a reduction in Bacteroidetes and Clostridium, and an increase in Firmicutes, Akkermansia, and Euryarchaeota (Miyake et al., 2015; Jangi et al., 2016). Loss of SCFA–producing bacteria and a reduction in Prevotella correlate with inflammation and disease activity in RRMS. In experimental autoimmune encephalomyelitis, transplantation of MS microbiota into mice exacerbates disease, while FMT from healthy donors alleviates pathology (Berer et al., 2017, Cekanaviciute et al., 2017). Untreated MS patients exhibited elevated levels of Akkermansia, which promotes proinflammatory responses, whereas the loss of Clostridium clusters reduces SCFA secretion and disrupts immune regulation (Miyake et al., 2015; Jangi et al., 2016).

Probiotics and Prebiotics in Restoring Gut Microbial Balance

Probiotics are *live beneficial microorganisms* (commonly species of Lactobacillus, Bifidobacterium, and Saccharomyces) that, when administered in adequate amounts, confer health benefits to the host. They help restore a balanced gut microbiome by competing with pathogenic microbes for nutrients and adhesion sites, enhancing intestinal barrier integrity, producing

antimicrobial substances and beneficial metabolites (e.g., short-chain fatty acids) and modulating immune responses and reducing inflammation (Sarita et al., 2025). Prebiotics on the other hand, are *non-digestible dietary fibers* (e.g., inulin, fructo oligosaccharides, galacto oligosaccharides) that selectively stimulate the growth and activity of beneficial gut bacteria. Prebiotics contribute to gut health by enhancing the abundance of beneficial microbes such as Bifidobacteria, increasing production of short-chain fatty acids, which promote gut epithelial health and supporting improved intestinal motility and metabolic balance. Probiotics also enhance insulin sensitivity by modulating the gut microbiota, reducing intestinal permeability, and decreasing the production of proinflammatory cytokines (Y. A. Kim et al., 2018; Li et al., 2020). Nonetheless, the efficacy of probiotics may be population-specific. For example, probiotic supplementation did not prevent gestational diabetes mellitus in overweight and obese women, underscoring the influence of hormonal factors.

Symbiotic therapy, the combination of probiotics and prebiotics, can have synergistic effects by providing both beneficial microbes and substrates that promote their growth. This approach is used to support gut microbial homeostasis, reduce gastrointestinal disorders, and influence systemic immune and metabolic function (Kumari et al., 2024).

Dietary Interventions

Diets abundant in fiber—especially those including fruits, vegetables and fermented foods—support higher microbial diversity and greater short-chain fatty acid (SCFA) production, whereas dietary patterns high in fat but low in fiber are linked to reduced microbiome health and altered microbial function (Zeng et al., 2025).

Fecal Microbiota Transplantation

Fecal microbiota transplantation is the transfer of stool from a healthy donor into a recipient's gut to restore microbial balance. This has proven highly effective for treating recurrent *Clostridioides difficile* infection (rCDI) and is now being studied for conditions such as inflammatory-bowel disease and metabolic disorders (Baydoun et al., 2025).

Next-Generation Therapeutics

Recent developments in microbiome-based therapies are moving beyond standard probiotics and prebiotics, including engineered probiotics, synbiotics (combined probiotic + prebiotic formulations), and precision microbiome editing techniques aimed at modifying microbial functions and communities in a controlled manner. Synthetic biology applies engineering principles to the biological realm, employing cutting-edge genome-

editing tools such as CRISPR-Cas systems, TALENs and Zinc Finger Nucleases (ZFNs) to create novel biological systems with precision—enabling applications across medicine, agriculture and environmental science (Zheng et al., 2024).

Future Directions and Challenges

Despite significant progress in understanding the gut microbiota's role in human health and disease, major challenges remain in translating these insights into clinical practice. A primary limitation is the variability of microbiota composition across individuals, influenced by diet, genetics, environment, age, and geography (David et al., 2014; Ursell et al., 2014). Future studies should prioritize longitudinal and multi-omic approaches integrating metagenomics, metabolomics, and transcriptomics to uncover mechanistic pathways linking microbial communities to host physiology (132). Standardization of sampling, sequencing, and data analysis methods is essential to enhance reproducibility and enable cross-cohort comparisons (Eckburg et al., 2005). Establishing causal relationships between microbial taxa or metabolites and disease outcomes, rather than mere associations, also remains a critical challenge, necessitating the use of germ-free models, humanized mice, and well-controlled intervention trials (Sampson et al., 2020).

Therapeutically, precision microbiome modulation through diet, prebiotics, probiotics, or fecal microbiota transplantation (FMT) offers promising potential, yet optimal dosing, duration, and safety profiles require further (70). Additionally, microbial metabolites such as short-chain fatty acids, bile acids, and trimethylamine-N-oxide represent novel biomarkers and therapeutic targets that warrant deeper metabolic characterization (Nho et al., 2019). Integration of microbiome data into predictive disease models could enable early detection and personalized interventions for metabolic, neurodegenerative, and autoimmune disorders (Jain et al., 2023). Nonetheless, ethical considerations, including data privacy, microbial patenting, and equitable access to microbiome-based therapies, must be addressed to ensure responsible translation of research into public health benefits. Collectively, future research should adopt a systems-level approach that connects diet, host genetics, and microbial function to advance microbiota-driven precision medicine and sustainable disease prevention strategies.

CONCLUSION

The gut microbiota is an integral component of human health, influencing a wide range of physiological functions and disease processes. As evidence mounts linking microbial balance to health outcomes, targeting the gut

microbiota offers promising avenues for disease prevention, diagnosis, and therapy. A deeper understanding of the microbiota's complexities will pave the way for innovative and personalized approaches in modern medicine.

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